

DIABETES AND CHILDREN**Jo'rayeva Gulhayo Jalol qizi**

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Abstract. *This article provides general information about the clinic for children with diabetes.*

Key words: *type 1 diabets, insulin, pancreas, glucose, dehydration, thirst, frequent urination, headache, blurred vision, frequent feeding, fatigue, weight loss, nervousness.*

ДИАБЕТ И ДЕТИ

Аннотация. *В статье дана общая информация о клинике для детей с диабетом.*

Ключевые слова: *диабет 1 типа, инсулин, поджелудочная железа, глюкоза, обезвоживание, жажда, частое мочеиспускание, головная боль, нечеткость зрения, частое кормление, усталость, потеря веса, нервозность.*

Introduction: Diabetes is a disease caused by insulin deficiency and damage to the body.

Diabetes has been known for a long time in the history of Eastern folk medicine. Abu Ali ibn Sina pays special attention to this pain. "Water comes out the way you drink it," he wrote. The patient's drinking a lot of water also produces another builder, and the patient loses a lot of weight.

Diabetes is a chronic, metabolic disease characterized by elevated levels of blood glucose (or blood sugar), which leads over time to serious damage to the heart, blood vessels, eyes, kidneys and nerves. The most common is type 2 diabetes, usually in adults, which occurs when the body becomes resistant to insulin or doesn't make enough insulin. In the past 3 decades the prevalence of type 2 diabetes has risen dramatically in countries of all income levels. Type 1 diabetes, once known as juvenile diabetes or insulin-dependent diabetes, is a chronic condition in which the pancreas produces little or no insulin by itself. For people living with diabetes, access to affordable treatment, including insulin, is critical to their survival.

Nowadays, the number of children with diabetes is increasing. Type 1 diabetes is often diagnosed in patients under the age of 30, and the peak of the disease occurs at the age of 14. Type 1 diabetes occurs when the pancreas cannot produce insulin, and the disease progresses very quickly. At such a time, we need to know the symptoms of the disease in order to provide timely help to the child.

Materials and methods The first type of diabetes develops suddenly, how, gradually.

There is also an asymptomatic type of the disease. Both types of diabetes have different symptoms, but they also have common symptoms:

constant dry mouth, constant thirst, sometimes the patient can drink from seven to ten liters of water a day;

a lot and frequent urination (polyuria);

appetite (polyphagia);

register, soreness/dryness of direct use, the appearance of purulent lesions on the skin and regeneration;

severe fatigue, insomnia, consequences of physical and mental activity;

poor eyesight;

seizures.

When there is too much glucose in the blood, the body may try to pass it through the urine. Dehydration occurs in the body and the child becomes thirsty.

The higher the level of sugar in the blood, the more often the child has a headache. In addition, the eyesight deteriorates in adolescents. All children can eat a lot, because the growing organism requires more nutrients. This is due to the lack of insulin, glucose accumulates in the blood, does not enter the cells and does not participate in energy production. That is why the child always feels hungry. If there is no glucose in the cells, not enough energy is produced. As a result, fatigue increases in the body. You may not have enough energy for the tasks you used to perform.

Most people think that people with diabetes are overweight. But this is not always the case.

Glucose-starved cells destroy muscle tissue and fat reserves to provide energy, and the patient begins to lose weight. Of course, mood swings are normal for most teenagers. A small study conducted by the American Diabetes Association in 2007 found that children became more moody and irritable when their blood sugar levels were high.

Conclusion: If we pay attention to the above signs, we will detect type 1 diabetes early.

By starting treatment in time, we can prevent complications of the disease and prolong life.

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